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TECHNOLOGY
VHDL IMPLIMENTATION OF PARALLEL MULTIPLIERS BASED ON
MODIFIED BOOTH ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT

Multipliers are playing a vital role in DSP and Neural Networks applications. Many methods have been introduced to work on multipliers that offer high speed, less power consumption and reduced area. Booth Algorithm demonstrates an efficient way of signed binary multiplication. In this paper, physical design of radix4,radix-8 and radix16 booth multiplier for signed multiplication is presented with an aim to improve the performance metrics such as power, area and delay. The performance of radix4, radix-8 booth multiplier is compared with the radix-16 booth multiplier. Low power consumption and small area are some of the most important criteria for design of any high performance systems. So in this paper the best solution to the problem is determined by designing a high speed multiplier chiefly booth multiplier which reduces the number of flip flops and memory size in the design circuitry as compared to conventional serial multiplier. Then implementation of a calculator using booth multiplier and several other operational modules is done using codes written in VHDL language using ISE XILINX 14.7 and simulated in MODEL SIM.

KEYWORDS: Booth Multiplier, Radix8, Radix16, Multipliers.

1. INTRODUCTION

Binary multiplier is a combinational logic circuit to perform multiplication of two binary numbers. The two binary numbers are more explicitly known as multiplicand and multiplier and the outcome is known as a product. The multiplicand and multiplier can be available in variety of bit sizes. The number of bits required to represent product can be Estimated depending on the bit sizes required for the multiplicand and multiplier. The addition of the bit sizes of multiplicand and multiplier is equal to the total bit size of the product. Binary multiplication involves following steps:

1. Re-coding of the bits in a multiplier within a particular number configuration.
2. The multiplication of every bit in a multiplier can be multiplied with the multiplicand, producing no. of products
3. Reduce the partial product range using multi operand accumulation technique.
4. The two operands can be added by using carry propagate adder to get the ultimate result.

Recoding method is used to determine the no. of partial products. The re-coding process recodes binary information into signed bit information. The partial products generated for convention modified booth encoding is $n/2+1$ instead of $n/2$. Addition of extra 1bit at the LSB of partial product. This leads to unequal partial product array. In radix-q ($q=2m$) the binary operand is collected of unnecessary radix-q digits. Radix-4 is a commonly used modified booth re-coding method that recodes operands into set $\{-2,-1, 0, 1, 2\}$. This is a widely used re-coding because it requires simple shifts and complementation to get partial products. Different variations of booth algorithm for recording circuitry and the adder for final compression of partial products are implemented.. The proposed architecture was synthesized using Xilinx tool. Based on the theoretical and experimental estimation, analysis was carried on results such as the amount of hardware resources and delay . Proposed multipliers can be used for high performance applications like signal processing, image processing.

In general, a multiplier uses Booth's algorithm and array of full adders (FAs), or Wallace tree instead of the array of FAs., i.e., this multiplier mainly consists of three parts: Booth encoder, a tree to compress the partial products such as Wallace tree, and final adder. To reduce the number of calculation steps for the partial products, MBA algorithm has been applied mostly where Wallace tree has taken the role of increasing the speed to add the partial products.

The booth algorithm was first introduced by Andrew Donald Booth in 1950, London. This algorithm was a study of computer architecture. This booth algorithm multiplies two signed binary digits in 2's complement form. This algorithm was introduced while doing research on crystallography. In booth algorithm less number of additions and subtractions can be observed. Booth multiplier is the faster multiplier in doing computations. This booth algorithm is widely used in ASIC products due to its smaller area and high computational speed[7-8]. The major steps in booth algorithm are: a. Generating the partial products b. Reducing the partial products c. Summation of the partial products In booth algorithm, the generation of partial products depends on recoding mechanism. The process uses booth recoding method based on the partial products that can be created for a set of 0's and 1's this is called Booths recoding. The main aim of this algorithm is to generate Partial products efficiently. There will be an rise of partial product[6] which depends on the Radix used for recoding. This recoding mechanism provides less power and area.

2. MODIFIED BOOTH MULTIPLIER

It is a powerful algorithm for signed-number multiplication, which treats both positive and negative numbers uniformly.

Booth algorithm is a method that will reduce the number of multiplicand multiples. For a given range of numbers to be represented, a higher representation radix leads to fewer digits. Since a k-bit binary number can be interpreted as K/2-digit radix-4 number, a K/3-digit radix-8 number, and so on, it can deal with more than one bit of the multiplier in each cycle by using high radix multiplication. The Modified Booth multiplier is an extension of Booth's multiplier. In Modified Booth, the number of partial products reduced by N/2, that is half of total partial products as compare to simple multiplication process [4].

Fig:- Block diagram for Modified Booth Multiplier

So, clearly if the Number of partial products becomes reduced, the area of the multiplier also will reduce and automatically as the result of it, the speed will increase. So, this multiplier is more efficient. Booth's algorithm is a procedure for the multiplication of two signed binary numbers in two's complement notation. This code is a structural\behavioral implementation of the N bit Booth's multiplier in VHDL.

Fig:- Parallel multiplier based on BOOTH's algorithm

The main structure of the file called BOOTHMUL is based on the replication of a base block (booth_add), which allows the application of the algorithm. This structure is shown below in the image.

Fig:- Parallel multiplier based on BOOTH's algorithm

It is possible to reduce the number of partial products by half, by using the technique of radix-4 Booth recoding. In this method, the multiplier is appended by „0“ in the LSB and then it is grouped in overlapping groups of three. Then based on the operations mentioned in the recoding table drawn below, multiplicand is altered to finally get the product. Here we get $(n/2)$ partial products for n bit multiplier where n is even. When n is odd, we get $((n/2)+1)$ partial products. So as we increase the number of overlapping bits in the multiplier (radix), partial products can be decreased. In this paper, partial products are formed using radix 4 multiplication process. When compared [10] Radix-4 Booth Multiplier gives higher speed when compared with Radix-2 Booth Multiplier. [11]The main disadvantage of the modified booth multiplier is its complexity to produce partial product.

Booth Multiplier (Radix 4):-

Radix-4 Modified Booth Encoder performs the process of encoding the multiplicand based on multiplier bits. It will compare 3 bits at a time with overlapping technique. Grouping starts from the LSB, and the first block only uses two bits of the multiplier and assumes a zero for the third bit. The detection unit has one of the two operands as its input to decide whether the Booth encoder calculates redundant computations. The functional operation of Radix-4 booth encoder is shown in the Table 1.

Fig:- Grouping of bits from multiplier term

In Radix-4 Modified Booth algorithm, the number of partial products reduced by half. For multiplication of 2's complement numbers, the two bit encoding using this algorithm scans a triplet of bits. To Booth recode the multiplier term, consider the bits in blocks of three, such that each block overlaps the previous block by one bit. Grouping starts from the LSB, and the first block only uses two bits of the multiplier. Figure 3 show the grouping of bits from the multiplier term in modified booth encoding. Each block is decoded to generate the correct partial product. The encoding of the multiplier Y, using the modified booth algorithm, generates the following five signed digits, -2, -1, 0, +1, +2. Each encoded digit in the multiplier performs a certain operation on the multiplicand, X, as illustrated in below table.

Block	Recoded Digit	Operation on X
000	0	0X
001	+1	+1X
010	+1	+1X
011	+2	+2X
100	-2	-2X
101	-1	-1X
110	-1	-1X
111	0	0X

Tab:- RADIX-4 BOOTH ENCODING

Booth Multiplier (Radix 8):-

This algorithm is similar to that of radix 4, but the only Difference is that we consider quartets of bits rather than that of triplets. This algorithm minimizes the number of partial products to n/3 where as in radix 4 it is reduced to n/2. This minimization of Partial products leads to fast computational speed and less power and area. Table1 represents the booth encoding table of Radix 8 booth recoding algorithm.[5]

Multiplier Bits				Operation on Multiplicand
A	B	C	D	X
0	0	0	0	0X
0	0	0	1	+1X
0	0	1	0	+1X
0	0	1	1	+2X
0	1	0	0	+2X
0	1	0	1	+3X
0	1	1	0	+3X
0	1	1	1	+4X
1	0	0	0	-4X
1	0	0	1	-3X
1	0	1	0	-3X
1	0	1	1	-2X
1	1	0	0	-2X
1	1	0	1	-1X
1	1	1	0	-1X
1	1	1	1	0X

Table: -Radix 8 Booth algorithm Encoding table

For example , an 8x8 bit radix 8 considering the signed bit as 1 and x as input data of 8-bit ; y as input data of 8-bit and k as the output data , x=11111111 y= 11111111 then k = 1111111111111111.

In this Radix-8, the multiplier(y) bits can be grouped into 4-bits in use at a time. Zero must be padded at right side of the multiplier operand. The 1st group of recoding digit is formed by padded bit and the remaining 3 bits are the 3 Least Significant bits of multiplier. The second group of recoding digit is formed by taking the starting bit as the MSB of 1st group and remaining 3 bits of Least Significant bits of multiplier. Below Fig.4 shows the grouping of bits for N=12 in Radix-8 booth multiplier. The Radix-8 algorithm generates the partial products are $n/8$. Consider multiplicand as x. Below Table 2 shows Modified booth encoding table for radix-8.

Fig:- Grouping of multiplier bits for N=12

Booth Multiplier (Radix 16):-

Describe briefly the architecture of the basic radix-16 Booth multiplier (see[7] for instance). For sake of simplicity, but without loss of generality, we consider unsigned operands with $n = 64$. Let us denote with X the multiplicand operand with bit components x_i ($i= 0$ to $n - 1$, with the least significant bit, LSB, at position 0) and with Y the multiplier operand and bit components y_i . The first step is the recoding of the multiplier operand [8]: groups of four bits with relative values in the set $\{0, 1, \dots, 14, 15\}$ are recoded to digits in the set $\{-8, -7, \dots, 0, \dots, 7, 8\}$ (minimally redundant radix-16 digit set to reduce the number of multiples). This recoding is done with the help of a transfer digit t_i and an interim digit w_i [7]. The recoded digit z_i is the sum of the interim and transfer digits $z_i = w_i + t_i$. When the value of the four bits, v_i , is less than 8, the transfer digit is zero and the interim digit $w_i = v_i$. For values of v_i greater than or equal to 8, v_i is transformed into $v_i = 16 - (16 - v_i)$, so that a transfer digit is generated to the next radix-16 digit position (t_{i+1}) and an interim digit of value $w_i = -(16 - v_i)$ is left. That is $0 \leq v_i < 8 : t_{i+1} = 0, w_i = v_i, w_i \in [0, 7]$; $8 \leq v_i \leq 15 : t_{i+1} = 1, w_i = -(16 - v_i), w_i \in [-8, -1]$. The transfer digit corresponds to the most significant bit (MSB) of the four-bit group, since this bit determines if the radix-16 digit is greater than or equal to 8. The final logical step is to add the interim digits and the transfer digits (0 or 1) from the radix-16 digit position to the right. Since the transfer digit is either 1 or 0, the addition of the interim digit and the transfer digit results in a final digit in the set $\{-8, -7, \dots, 0, \dots, 7, 8\}$. Due to a possible transfer digit from the most significant radix-16 digit, the number of resultant radix-16 recoded digits is $\lfloor (n + 1)/4 \rfloor$. Therefore, for $n = 64$ the number of recoded digits (and the number of partial products) is 17. Note that the most significant digit is 0 or 1 because it is in fact just a transfer digit. After recoding, the partial products are generated by digit multiplication of the recoded digits times the multiplicand X.

For the set of digits $\{-8, -7, \dots, 0, \dots, 7, 8\}$, the multiples $1X, 2X, 4X,$ and $8X$ are easy to compute, since they are obtained by simple logic shifts. The negative versions of these multiples are obtained by bit inversion and addition of a 1 in the corresponding position in the bit array of the partial products. The generations of $3X, 5X,$ and $7X$ (odd multiples) require carry-propagate adders (the negative versions of these multiples are obtained as before). Finally, $6X$ is obtained by a simple one bit left shift of $3X$. Fig. 1 illustrates a possible implementation of the partial product generation. Five bits of the multiplier Y are used to obtain the recoded digit (four bits of one digit and one bit of the previous digit to determine the transfer digit to be added).

Fig:-. Partial product generation.

The resultant digit is obtained as a one-hot code to directly drive a 8 to 1 multiplexer with an implicit zero output (output equal to zero when all the control signals of the multiplexer are zero). The recoding requires the implementation of simple logic equations that are not in the critical q path due to the generation in parallel of the odd multiples (carry propagate addition). The XOR at the output of the multiplexer is for bit complementation (part of the computation of the two’s complement when the multiplier digit is negative). Fig. 2(a) illustrates part of the resultant bit array for n = 64 after the simplification of the sign extension [7].

Fig:-Radix16 Booth Encoder

❖ **Experimental Observations:-**

The experimental observations were carried out on Xilinx Vivado 2016.4 the HDL code was written in VHDL. Below shows the Technology schematic, RTL Schematic and wave forms of Radix-4 ,Radix-8 AND Radix-16 Booth multiplier.

1. Results of Radix-4 Booth Multiplier:-

For checking the operation of booth multiplier, we implement a test bench. Here we gave different series of inputs to the Booth Multiplier which produces the output.

A. Simulation timing diagram:-

B. RTL Schematic:-

C. Technology Schematic:-

2. Results of Radix-8Booth Multiplier:-

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For checking the operation of booth multiplier, we implement a test bench. Here we gave different series of inputs to the Booth Multiplier which produces the output.

a) Simulation timing diagram:-

b) . RTL Schematic:-

c) Technology Schematic:-

3. Results of Radix-4 Booth Wrapper Multiplier:-

For checking the operation of booth multiplier, we implement a test bench. Here we gave different series of inputs to the Booth Multiplier which produces the output.

Simulation timing diagram:-

II. RTL Schematic:-

III. Technology Schematic:-

4. Results of Radix-16 Booth Multiplier:-

For checking the operation of booth multiplier, we implement a test bench. Here we gave different series of inputs to the Booth Multiplier which produces the output.

a) Simulation timing diagram:-

b) RTL Schematic:-

c) Technology Schematic:-

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:-

The device utilization summaries represents the number of LUT, slices, muxes, flip-flops, bonded IOB etc., are utilized and available in the design by which we can have a knowledge of how much area in the chip is utilized

by our design. The device utilization summary of Radix-4, Radix-8 and Radix-16 Booth multiplier can be observed in below Table.

Resource	Utilization	Available
LUT	20	2400
FF	20	20
IO	16	102
DELAY	8.571	

Table :- Device utilization of Radix-4 booth Multiplier

Resource	Utilization	Available
LUT	40	2400
FF	20	20
IO	20	102
DELAY	9.311NS	

Table :- Device utilization of Radix-8 booth Multiplier

Resource	Utilization	Available
LUT	20	2400
FF	20	20
IO	18	102
DELAY	9.150NS	

Table :- Device utilization of Radix-4 wrapper booth Multiplier

Resource	Utilization	Available
LUT	35	2400
FF	35	35
IO	36	102
DELAY	7.999NS	

Table :- Device utilization of Radix-16 booth Multiplier

4. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE :-

In this paper, we clear the concept of different multiplier and their implementation on the basis of modified Booth algorithm. We found that the Parallel multipliers are much option than the other multiplier. We concluded this from the simulation and synthesis result. In case of parallel multipliers, the total area is much less than that of other multipliers. Hence the power consumption is also less. This is clearly depicted in our results. This speeds up the calculation and makes the system faster. In this paper Booth Radix-4, Radix-8 and 16 Multiplier is designed. In Radix-16 Multiplier delay time and area is high which is found reduced at 7.999 ns and 35 slices respectively using Booth Radix-4 and 8 Multiplier. The simulation results prove that the designed architecture is more efficient than the conventional one in terms of area and delay. Therefore, designed Booth Multiplier architecture is low area, high speed, simple and efficient for VLSI hardware implementation. Due to efficient performance of designed Booth Multiplier with FSM, a tradeoff occurred between delay, area and speed. While comparing the Radix-4, Radix-8 and the Radix-16 booth multipliers we found that Radix-16 generates lesser number of partial products as compare to Radix-8. So the Radix-16 is used for Most of Low Power design systems. At the end we calculate and compare the delay of various multipliers and concluded that for the minimal power design of multiplier Radix-16 multiplier should be used as the delay of Radix-16 multiplier lesser as compare to other multipliers like Radix-8.

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